

The Influence of *Miyang* Tradition on Children's Learning Motivation in Coastal Areas

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ABSTRACT: The research was conducted in the coastal area of Tuban Regency with the aim of analysing the influence of *Miyang* culture on the learning motivation of fishermen's children in coastal Tuban, knowing the factors that can affect children's learning motivation, and knowing the influence of Rumah Baca on the learning motivation of fishermen's children in Karangsari coastal Tuban. The *Miyang* culture that exists in three coastal areas in Tuban Regency causes an influence on the different levels of learning motivation. This research uses literature, observation and interviews with fishermen's children in the coastal areas of Tuban. About 10 informants were interviewed and the data collection process was conducted over two weeks. It shows that coastal children have different levels of learning motivation, the east and west coastal areas tend to have low learning motivation, but in the central area, children are more likely to have quite good learning motivation. Influencing factors are the environment and family support, many children have gone to *Miyang* to earn money. With the presence of *Rumah Baca Pesisir Cerdas*, one of the reading houses in Karangsari Tuban, it has an influence on students' learning motivation. *Rumah Baca Pesisir Cerdas* increases learning motivation with the results of data analysis of the number of students who actively participate in activities, and children dare to have high ideals and enthusiasm for school.

KEYWORDS: miyang culture, learning motivation, reading park

I. INTRODUCTION

The coast is an area located on the beach. The coastal area is characterised by densely populated settlements. The majority of people who live on the coast earn a living as fishermen. This is the case with the people of Tuban, the people who live on the coast call the tradition *Miyang*. The geographical condition of Tuban Regency is divided into three coastal areas, namely the coastal area located in the eastern part of Tuban Regency, the coastal area located in the central part of Tuban Regency, and the coastal area located in the western part of Tuban Regency. The eastern area is the Palang sub-district, the central area is the Jenu and Tuban sub-districts, and the western area is the Tambakboyo and Bancar sub-districts, each of these coastal areas has its own characteristics. The characteristics of these areas cause differences in the economic, social and cultural conditions of the community.

According to Mahsun (1995), the coastal area is intended or the same as being called the fishermen, this is because most people in the coastal area work or work as fishermen. These fishermen are called human operations in the sea who look for fish with other humans. The fish is later sold at the fish market, and uses a vehicle in the form of a boat [1]. These fishermen call their fishing activities *Miyang*. The three coastal areas, west and centre, are referred to by the same term.

Miyang is a livelihood carried out by the community, *Miyang* or known as fishing with traditional equipment. It is a livelihood that has been done for generations. The marine resources of the Tuban area are a livelihood sector that can be used to meet the needs of fishermen. So that it becomes a livelihood that is often passed down to generations of fishermen. Most of the fishermen, when they have sons, tend to introduce and teach them to do *miyang* activities since childhood, so that the majority of the fishermen's children continue their parents' profession as fishermen. Meanwhile, female children are also involved in selling their parents' sea catches.

The fishing profession is a profession that is carried out in a trained manner, to be able to go to sea children need to be trained and need experience from their parents. Therefore, with children often following their parents to join *Miyang*, the motivation to study of the fishermen's children decreases. Most children stop going to school until junior high school, and there are also those who go to high school, but there are still not many children who go to university.

Along with economic development in the Tuban area, with the emergence of the industrial sector in Tuban district. Coastal areas face various pressures and developments and changes [2]. The view of the hereditary profession of being a fisherman has begun to change, but this does not apply to all coastal areas in Tuban. In areas located in the range close to the industry, it is a factor in the

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emergence of learning motivation for fishermen's children. This is due to the motivation for fishermen's children to be able to get a job as an employee in the industry around the coast. The coastal area close to the industrial area is in the central part of Tuban district, namely the coastal area in Jenu sub-district. Although parents in this area still earn a living as fishermen, the children of fishermen already have a lot of developed thinking, many of them choose to continue their schooling and choose to work in the industrial sector.

In contrast to the community in the Karangasari area of Tuban sub-district, the learning motivation of children in this area is still low. Many children still follow their parents' work as fishermen. They have been fishing since they finished junior high school, so this has caused many children in the Karangasari coastal area to only continue their education until junior high school. With the condition of this problem in the Karangasari area, a reading house called Rumah Baca Pesisir Cerdas (FGPB) was established. The reading house aims to increase interest in reading, and increase the knowledge of coastal children, with the hope of increasing motivation to learn and continue school.

From some of the descriptions above, the environment has an influence on the learning motivation of coastal children. With the diversity of factors that cause differences in learning motivation in coastal areas in Tuban district, motivates the author to conduct a review and analysis of these problems. So that it can produce useful information.

Miyang Culture

Miyang is a term from the community for those who devote themselves to working at sea [3]. *Miyang* is carried out by male parents who are used as a livelihood to support the family, but it is not uncommon for fishermen in coastal areas in Karangasari Tuban to introduce and teach their sons to join *Miyang*. *Miyang* by going to sea requires only skills gained from frequent training, without special competency requirements and exams, so the children of fishermen assume that by going to sea alone they can get wages or money from selling *Miyang* products. The majority of the catch from *Miyang* is sold at the Fish Plaza in Karangasari area, Tuban sub-district.

Most *Miyang* in Tuban is carried out by fishermen starting at night and they will go ashore during the day. After landing the fishermen will directly sell their seafood to the middlemen, and the fishermen will get income according to their results at sea. The environment of the Karangasari coastal area is a densely populated area like other coastal areas in Tuban Regency. In the season of abundant sea catches, they often call it *along*, on the other hand, when their catches are small, the community calls it *laib*.

Learning Motivation

The definition of Learning Motivation according to Sudirman 2011, that learning motivation is the overall driving force within students that raises, ensures continuity, provides direction for learning activities, so that it is hoped that goals can be achieved [4]. According to Winkel (in Aina Mulyana, 2018) defines learning motivation as all efforts within oneself that give rise to learning activities, and ensure the continuity of learning activities and give direction to learning activities so that the desired goals are achieved. Motivation to learn is a psychological factor that is non-intellectual and plays a role in terms of fostering a spirit of learning for individuals [4].

Learning motivation is needed to be a benchmark for the success of an education, because good learning motivation at school age will provide a correlation to the enthusiastic spirit to learn and complete the education process, one of the factors that affect the success of student learning at school is motivation. Motivation will have an impact on student learning outcomes, either directly or indirectly. Every student has a goal in his activity, so he will have strong motivation to achieve it. Utilising all efforts will be made to achieve their learning dreams [5]. The environment, which is a learning resource, has an influence on the learning process [6]. The environment of fishermen's children to build their learning motivation requires motivation and the role of the family, especially the parents, the factors that best support the success of children's education include the most dominant role of parents [7].

Motivation and learning are two things that are interrelated and have a strong influence on one another. Motivation to learn arises because of intrinsic factors, namely in the form of desire and desire to succeed and drive learning needs. The extrinsic factor is the recognition of a conducive, comfortable and interesting learning environment. Learning motivation is essentially an internal and external drive in students with supporting indicators. This kind of encouragement has a big role for one's success in learning (Uno. 2011: 140), [8]. The success of children's education is not determined by life background or social status, but is strongly influenced by the role of the family, which is the main motivator in instilling a set of successes that need to be planned for the future [7].

Motivation from previous research, it was also found that there are several things that cause some to have low learning motivation and not attend school, namely as follows: 1.From an economic point of view, 2.Lack of parental awareness of the importance of education [3].

Rumah Baca Or Community Reading Garden

Rumah Baca Pesisir Cerdas is a reading park or a community social movement. *Taman Baca* is a place to facilitate the community in obtaining learning facilities and information in the form of reading materials and other library materials. *Taman Baca* has a concept of, by, and for the community. All levels of society have the right to use *Taman Baca* regardless of social,

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economic, religious, cultural, age, and educational backgrounds [9]. *Rumah Baca Pesisir Cerdas*, provides stimulation for children to have a culture of reading and increase knowledge to increase motivation to learn and to continue school. Social activities carried out at *Rumah Baca Pesisir Cerdas* are reading books, listening to stories and various other educational activities that attract children to attend and read at *Rumah Baca Pesisir Cerdas*.

II. METHODS

This research uses several qualitative methods, Sugiyono (2014: 1) states that qualitative research methods are research methods used to examine natural objects, where the researcher is the key instrument, data collection techniques are triangulated, data analysis is inductive, and qualitative research results emphasize meaning rather than generalisation [10].

The stages of the method carried out by researchers, first the literature method. Collecting written data from existing literature including data sourced from social networks. Furthermore, the interview method was used [11]. Interviews were conducted with informants who were categorised as children in the three coastal areas, namely the eastern coastal area, data obtained from the Palang sub-district, from the central part of the data obtained from the Tuban and Jenu sub-districts, and the western area data obtained from the Tambakboyo sub-district. The subjects used were interviewed with the distribution of acquisition focused on the location of Karang Sari Tuban. Each informant has a different way of interviewing. Especially for children, the interview was conducted using storytelling techniques and digging questions, in order to build a comfortable rapport for the child. This is with the intention of not causing fear in children. They do not feel like they are being interrogated. Just relax while telling stories and having conversations. The next step was observation. Observations have been conducted for approximately 2 weeks.

Observations are intended to reveal the actions and social behaviour of the object under study. Observations were made in the Karang Sari Tuban coastal beach area. Data collection techniques used observation, documentation, and interviews. Data analysis used interactive model according to Miles and Huberman. The data validity checking technique used triangulation techniques of theory, source and method [10]. Then the auxiliary instrument in this research is in the form of a recorder such as a mobile phone, or writing which is useful to help the research process.

III. RESULTS

The environment is a factor in student learning motivation, *Miyang* for parents has an impact on the learning motivation of children on the coast. From some data obtained from the results of interviews that have been conducted, that not all coastal areas in Tuban district fishermen's children have low learning motivation. In coastal areas close to industrial areas, fishermen's children have a high motivation to study and continue their education, due to the hope of being able to work in the industrial sector that is developing in the coastal area. This condition is different from fishermen in the Karang Sari Tuban area, the majority of children have low motivation to learn, this is due to a lack of support from the family environment.

To improve learning motivation, students also need encouragement from the environment. If family support factors do not provide enough support for the learning motivation of coastal children, then the role of the environment is needed. The mindset that has been developing for generations, that the children of coastal areas in Karang Sari Tuban, earn money by not having to study, they just need to practice and follow their parents' way to go *Miyang*. Meanwhile, learning motivation can still grow despite having to complete educational processes that require thought. Children with high learning motivation tend to have the enthusiasm to continue to a higher level of education. While children with low learning motivation, they will do easy things to get something without having to learn. Meanwhile, according to Sardiman (2006: 83), motivation in a person has characteristics including perseverance in facing tasks, resilience in facing difficulties (not easily discouraged), showing interest in various problems, preferring to work independently, not getting bored quickly with routine tasks, being able to defend his opinion, not giving up quickly on what he believes, and enjoying looking for and solving problem problems [12].

Children's motivation to learn in the Karang Sari Tuban area, despite the lack of support from parents, needs intervention actions that can be created by the community as an external factor. One of them is the existence of educational institutions and community reading parks that can provide facilities to access knowledge through literacy and reading parks. *Rumah Baca Pesisir Cerdas* is a reading park or community social movement. *Taman Baca* is a place to facilitate the community in obtaining learning facilities and information in the form of reading materials and other library materials. *Taman Baca* has a concept from, by and for the community. All levels of society have the right to use *Taman Baca* regardless of social, economic, religious, cultural, age and educational backgrounds [9]. The smart coastal reading park in Karang Sari Tuban, spearheaded by two young people in the neighbourhood, the background is due to concerns that are considered due to an environment that is less supportive to increase children's learning motivation.

From the activities that have taken place at the Community Reading Park, *Rumah Baca Pesisir Cerdas*, provides stimulation for children to have a culture of reading and increase knowledge to increase motivation to learn and to continue school. Social activities carried out at *Rumah Baca Pesisir Cerdas* are reading books, listening to stories and various other educational activities such as playing traditional games. which attracts children to attend and read at *Rumah Baca Pesisir Cerdas*.

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IV. DISCUSSION

According to Sudaryono (2012: 125), that to find out how much student interest in learning can be measured through: liking, interest, attention and involvement. Likeability can be seen from students' enthusiasm in participating in lessons. Interest can be measured from a person's response to respond to something. Attention can be measured if someone has seriousness during the learning process. Anitah, 2007 said that attention arises driven by curiosity. Attention is the concentration of psychic energy or thoughts and feelings towards an object. Learners who have an interest in an object will tend to pay greater attention to the material they are learning [13].

Children's attention and interest in visiting Rumah Baca Pesisir Cerdas is shown by their active participation in meetings organised at the reading house. From interviews obtained from parents whose children participated in activities at the Rumah Baca Pesisir Cerdas, parents felt that the children gained many benefits. Children become more enthusiastic to learn, and participate in activities. This is in accordance with previous research, that community involvement in the learning process can make extrinsic motivation [14]. Parents feel more helped by the existence of Rumah Baca Pesisir Cerdas which was established by the community. In addition, the children's mindset began to be awakened to dare to have ideals. From the results of questions and answers that took place during classroom observations, children dared to say that they had aspirations, such as the TNI, Police, Teachers, Doctors and Entrepreneurs, almost none of the children wanted to aspire to be fishermen like their parents, in line with an expert's explanation that the factors that influence learning motivation include the aspiration factor [15]. Previous research has found teacher support to be the 'best predictor' of students' aspirations to continue schooling [16]. By daring to have ideals, children will always be motivated to learn.

Although the presence of a Reading House on the coast has not been able to encourage children to have curiosity through reading, and provide stimulants for children to grow motivation to learn, but for coastal children who regularly visit the reading house has an impact on him. This is indicated by the intensity of children's visits, and the number of children visiting each week. The presence of the Rumah Baca Pesisir Cerdas community reading park, for some parents whose children visit the reading park, encourages them to support their children, still allowing their children to take part in activities at *Rumah Baca Pesisir Cerdas*.

V. CONCLUSIONS

Miyang is a term used by the community for those who devote themselves to working at sea. The children of fishermen in Karangasari Tuban mostly follow their parents' profession to join *Miyang*. This has an impact on children's learning motivation. Learning motivation can still grow with the influence of intrinsic factors, and extrinsic factors, namely the recognition of a conducive, comfortable and interesting learning environment. Learning motivation is essentially an internal and external drive in students with supporting indicators. Children with high learning motivation tend to have the enthusiasm to continue to a higher level of education. To foster learning motivation in addition to internal factors of parental support, social support is also needed in the form of the environment. One of them is with educational institutions and social activities in the form of reading parks. The reading park in Karangasari Tuban, known as Rumah Baca Pesisir Cerdas, can provide social support to foster children's curiosity and motivation to learn.

Hopefully this paper can provide benefits to readers with similar backgrounds and research objectives. In writing this work, the obstacle is the lack of journals supporting learning motivation for children on the coast.

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